

RELIABILITY ASSESSMENT OF PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE TECHNIQUES FOR MARINE PROPULSION SYSTEMS

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Abstract: *The maintainability and reliability of marine propulsion systems is critical for the operational efficiency, safety, and economic feasibility of maritime operations and activities. This study aims to assess the reliability of predictive maintenance techniques employed for early detection of defects in marine propulsion systems to reduce breakdowns and downtime. The model integrated a reliability framework with field data gathered from the case study of Tugboat Abun to facilitate risk-informed repair prioritization for the reliability of the vessel's marine propulsion system. This will use the ANN-based prediction model with FTA and FMECA for risk-informed maintenance prioritization towards reliability of the marine propulsion system and assess the effectiveness of the combined ANN-FTA-FMECA framework in reducing downtime, extending equipment service life, and lowering operational costs on marine propulsion systems. The model's prediction for the injectors of the starboard propulsion plant of the vessel averaged 95 percent, with a mean square error of 12.13 and a mean absolute error of 3.13, signifying that the predictions were, on average, highly accurate relative to the actual values. The subsystem failure probability graph shows the relative vulnerability of each component group contributing to the overall propulsion system unreliability. The highest probability was observed in the fuel system ($P = 0.1817$), indicating it as the most failure-prone subsystem due to frequent occurrences such as injector and filter blockages. This was followed by the engine block assembly ($P = 0.1299$) and main engine cooling system ($P = 0.0672$), both critical for maintaining propulsion stability and thermal regulation. Moderate failure probabilities were recorded in gearbox cooling ($P = 0.0580$) and main engine lubricating oil system ($P = 0.0390$), signifying poor cooling and inadequate lubrication (viscosity loss). Subsystems such as shafting ($P = 0.0065$),*

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coupling, bearing, and propeller ($P = 0.0000$) show near-negligible probabilities, implying effective structural reliability. Overall, the combined subsystem probabilities yielded a top event probability ($P_{top} = 0.5882$), suggesting above-average overall system reliability. The results demonstrate that the Artificial Neural Network predictive model, utilizing the multi-layer perceptron architecture, can accurately forecast marine machinery breakdown, hence improving dependability and reducing downtime.

Introduction

The reliability of marine propulsion systems is fundamental to the operational efficiency, safety, and economic viability of maritime activities. These systems, encompassing main engines, gearboxes, shafts, and associated equipment, form the core of a vessel's ability to operate reliably across varying environments (Youssef et al., 2024; Peng, 2024; Neesae et al., 2026). Modern advances in data-driven engineering have inspired a shift towards condition-based and Predictive Maintenance (PdM) strategies that assess equipment health in real-time, allowing maintenance interventions to be performed only when justified by actual equipment status (Pagán et al., 2019; Ajinwo et al., 2025). This shift has been made possible by advances in sensor technologies, Machine Learning (ML), and statistical reliability methods. In this context, Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) have emerged as a highly effective tool for PdM due to their ability to process multi-dimensional sensor data and detect complex, latent patterns indicative of equipment degradation long before failure

occurs (Sun et al., 2024). An ANN-based approach enables maintenance personnel to move beyond static thresholds and instead learn from the dynamics of equipment operation across a range of environments, making them well-suited for the unpredictable and highly variable conditions common in marine propulsion (Guo & Zhang, 2023). These advances operate within a broader reliability engineering framework that includes established methods such as Fault Tree Analysis (FTA) and Failure Mode, Effects, and Criticality Analysis (FMECA). FTA provides a structured, hierarchical approach for understanding equipment failures by mapping cause-and-effect relationships within a system (Sezer et al., 2022). FMECA, by contrast, focuses on identifying critical modes of failure, assessing their potential effects, and prioritizing interventions based upon the severity and likelihood of their occurrence (Garbatov & Georgiev, 2024). When used in tandem, these methods enable a comprehensive understanding of reliability, focusing both on systemic vulnerability and component-level risk prioritization.

More recently, the application of ANN within this reliability engineering framework has created a powerful synthesis. ANN can learn from the qualitative and quantitative insights offered by FTA and FMECA, allowing PdM to move from post-event risk assessment towards forward-looking forecasting (Lazakis et al., 2018). This integrative approach improves the precision of maintenance planning, aligning interventions with actual equipment state and predicted degradation patterns (Ahmed et al., 2023). The result is a dynamic, data-driven maintenance approach that can adapt to highly variable operating conditions, making it especially suited to the marine sector, where environmental forces, load fluctuations, and equipment ageing are complex and interdependent (Daya & Lazakis, 2023). In this evolving context, ANN-based PdM, supported by FTA and FMECA, emerges as a key enabler for achieving higher reliability and longer service intervals for marine propulsion equipment (Simion et al., 2023). The purpose of this study is to build on these advances, developing an ANN-driven PdM supported by FTA and FMECA for a marine propulsion system. Its focus is to enhance reliability and reduce downtime, aligning theoretical advances and data-driven strategies with the practical constraints and operational demands of the marine propulsion systems.

This study aims to utilize reliability tools to evaluate predictive maintenance techniques for marine propulsion systems, thereby enhancing

reliability and minimizing downtime. This will integrate the ANN-based prediction model with FTA and FMECA for risk-informed maintenance prioritization towards reliability of the marine propulsion system and assess the effectiveness of the combined ANN-FTA-FMECA framework in reducing downtime, extending equipment service life, and lowering operational costs on marine propulsion systems. Marine propulsion systems are essential for the smooth operation of ships. Increasing the efficiency of marine propulsion systems will result in reduced fuel consumption and the sustainability of the maritime industry (Tamunodukobipi & Nitonye 2019; Afini et al 2025).

Figure 1 provides a schematic illustration of a typical inboard marine propulsion configuration, highlighting its key components and their relative positions. This depiction captures the hierarchical layout and allows for a clearer understanding of the relationship between engine, gearbox, shafting, and propeller within a marine propulsion assembly. Recent advances in technology have underscored the significance of reliability engineering and condition monitoring within marine propulsion systems. The growing availability of sensor technologies allows critical operational parameters, including vibration, pressure, temperature, and rotational speed, to be continuously monitored and analyzed (DNV & Propulsion Analytics, 2021). These advances enable the early detection of anomalies, making propulsion units ideal for PdM (Wärtsilä, 2019).

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Figure 1: General Configuration of a Marine Propulsion System
Fault Tree Analysis (FTA)

FTA is defined as a top-down, deductive technique used to identify and visualize the root causes of equipment failures within complex engineering environments (Ruijters & Stoelinga, 2015). Initially developed for aerospace and nuclear applications, FTA has been adopted across a range of industries due to its ability to depict hierarchical relationships between faults and assess their relative contribution to an undesired top-level event (Nolan, 2017). At its core, the technique begins with a defined top-level event, such as loss of propulsion, and systematically breaks down its outcome into basic causes, using a structure built on AND and OR gates to trace potential failure pathways.

In the context of marine propulsion systems, FTA provides a robust framework for identifying, categorizing, and assessing the root causes of equipment failures across critical subsystems, including main engines, gearboxes, shafts, and propeller assemblies. Recent advancements

have further strengthened the role of FTA within marine engineering. Kim et al. (2019) demonstrated that when combined with AI and ML, FTA can enable real-time risk assessment and anomaly detection within propulsion systems. Such integration allows maintenance teams to prioritize inspection and intervention efforts effectively, aligning resource allocation with equipment criticality and operational constraints.

Figure 2 illustrates an example of an FTA applied to a marine propulsion unit, capturing its hierarchical structure and the interplay between basic events and top-level outcomes. Through the visualisation and quantification of risk associated with critical equipment failures, FTA has become a cornerstone technique within reliability-centred and PdM programmes (Ruijters & Stoelinga, 2015). Its application is central to aligning maintenance strategies with operational demands and risk profiles, making it an essential method for achieving the aim of this study.

Figure 2: Example of Fault Tree Diagram for a Marine Propulsion System (Knežević et al., 2020)

Failure Mode and Effect Analysis/Criticality (FMECA)

FMEA is defined as a structured, bottom-up approach for identifying, assessing, and prioritizing potential equipment failures within complex engineering environments (Ruijters & Stoelinga, 2015). The task is generally performed by a team of experts, whereby each can express diverse opinions in rating of failure modes of systems, which may be in the form of precise data and imprecise distribution ratings (Emovon, 2016). The technique operates by identifying individual components within a system, determining their possible modes of failure, and assessing the effects of those failures upon the performance, reliability, and safety of the overall equipment. FMEA provides a systematic method for capturing equipment vulnerabilities and allows maintenance personnel to evaluate the relative significance of different failure modes

based upon their likelihood and potential impact (Simion et al., 2023).

Meanwhile, FMECA builds on the foundation of FMEA by introducing a criticality assessment, allowing engineering teams to prioritise identified failure modes based upon risk and operational significance. FMECA applies metrics such as the Risk Priority Number (RPN) or Criticality Index to assess both the severity and likelihood of specific failures, providing a more robust basis for maintenance planning (Simion et al., 2023). This approach allows maintenance resources to be aligned with equipment that has the highest risk profile, thereby facilitating cost-effective interventions and aligning maintenance activities closely with operational priorities.

In the context of marine propulsion, FMEA and FMECA have become vital tools for assessing and prioritizing the reliability and operational resilience of critical subsystems, including main and auxiliary engines, gearboxes, shafts, and

propeller assemblies (Daya & Lazakis, 2022). These methods enable engineering and maintenance teams to isolate dominant failure modes, assess their root causes, and implement targeted measures that reduce downtime, mitigate safety hazards, and maximise equipment availability. Modern advances have further strengthened the role of FMEA and FMECA within PdM environment. Daya and Lazakis (2022) highlighted how the integration of ANNs and ML techniques allows traditional FMECA methods to evolve into dynamic, data-driven risk assessment platforms. These enable maintenance teams to move from static reliability analyses to intelligent CBM that adapts to the actual state and performance of equipment.

Through these developments, FMEA and FMECA have evolved from traditional risk assessment tools into core elements of PdM strategies, aligning closely with the aim of this study. Their structured and data-driven approach provides a foundation upon which ANN-based PdM can be developed for marine propulsion systems, enhancing reliability, operational efficiency, and safety.

Mean Time between Failure (MTBF) and Risk Priority Number (RPN)

Mean Time between Failure (MTBF) is defined as a statistical measure of equipment reliability, representing the average operational period between successive failures of a component or system (Molęda et al., 2022). MTBF is calculated

by dividing total operational time by the number of failures observed within that period, yielding a measure of reliability that allows maintenance and engineering teams to assess equipment performance and anticipate intervention needs. In the context of marine propulsion systems, MTBF is critical for assessing the reliability of key equipment such as main and auxiliary engines, gearboxes, and propulsion shafts, where unanticipated downtime can have significant operational and financial consequences (Daya & Lazakis, 2024).

Although MTBF and RPN measure distinct aspects of equipment performance - MTBF providing a temporal measure of reliability and RPN offering a risk-based prioritisation metric, both have become integral to PdM practices (Elmdoost-Gashti et al., 2023). Advancements in data analytics, AI, and ML have enabled these metrics to evolve from static indicators to dynamic inputs within intelligent maintenance platforms (Zheng et al., 2020). Fazle et al. (2023) highlight how such advances now enable the continuous updating of MTBF and RPN based on real-time sensor data and operational conditions. Together, MTBF and RPN form the foundation for risk-aware, reliability-centered PdM for marine propulsion machinery. Their applications support the aim of this study, aligning maintenance interventions with equipment criticality and operational priorities.

Reliability Engineering Theory and Reliability Centre-Maintenance

Reliability engineering theory provides the statistical and theoretical foundation upon which maintenance decisions are made. Kiran (2017) defined reliability engineering as the discipline of quantifying equipment performance over time, assessing the likelihood of failures, and identifying strategies to ensure that assets operate within defined performance and safety limits. This theory applies statistical methods, including the analysis of failure rates, reliability metrics, and time-to-failure distributions, to characterize equipment behaviour and guide maintenance planning (Budimir et al., 2025).

The Weibull distribution, encapsulated within this formulation, has been extensively applied across engineering disciplines to model equipment reliability and justify maintenance policies. These statistical tools also relate closely to the Bathtub Curve, a fundamental reliability engineering model that characterizes equipment failure over time (de Assis et al., 2021). Modern risk theory also draws upon Bayesian statistical approaches, as advocated by Celeux et al. (2009) and later refined by Morato et al. (2020). These methods apply Bayesian updating to risk assessments, allowing maintenance decisions to evolve in response to new sensor data and equipment observations. Bayesian risk theory provides a dynamic, data-driven framework for prioritising maintenance interventions, aligning inspection and repair schedules with actual equipment condition and associated risk (Gupta et al., 2021; Fontalvo et al., 2024).

RCM Applications in Marine and Industrial Settings

Eriksen et al. (2021) conducted a comparative case study to assess the reliability challenges and maintenance needs associated with unmanned cargo ships, focusing on the applicability of traditional RCM methods within this emerging operational context. The researchers applied RCM to a critical machinery subsystem under both manned and unmanned conditions, combining qualitative analysis with failure probability assessments. Tripathi and Prasad (2024) conducted a study aimed at optimising maintenance strategies for marine diesel engines by integrating RCM with stochastic degradation modelling and genetic algorithms. The researchers performed FMEA and FTA to identify critical engine components, focusing particularly on journal bearings. They applied Markov models, based on condition-monitoring data such as vibration patterns, to capture performance degradation, and used a genetic algorithm to refine.

Condition-Based Maintenance and Prognostics Techniques

Wang et al. (2022) conducted a case study aimed at demonstrating how oil analysis data and stochastic filtering techniques can optimize maintenance scheduling for marine diesel engines. The researchers applied a CBM approach by extracting metal concentration data from oil samples collected across various marine diesel engines. Garbatov and Georgiev (2024)

conducted a study that aimed to develop an optimal maintenance planning method for ship propulsion systems by incorporating both equipment degradation dynamics and the International Maritime Organisation’s Carbon Intensity Indicator (CII). The researchers framed the maintenance decision-making process as a Markov Decision Process, representing the propulsion system’s state transitions across CII performance classes A–E.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this work, the data collected from the operating periods of the propulsion systems of Tug Abun, spanning from 2018 to 2023, serve as the foundational basis for the development of a predictive model aimed at evaluating and enhancing operational performance. To build effective predictive models and assess the reliability, a targeted selection of operational

parameters from the propulsion systems was made (Adumene & Nitonye, 2018). These parameters were carefully chosen based on their influence on the overall performance and reliability of the system. The selected parameters included variables such as engine speed, fuel consumption rate, shaft speed, oil pressure, and exhaust temperature.

These variables represent essential indicators of the propulsion system’s state and performance over time and provide insight into patterns of wear, efficiency fluctuations, and possible early signs of mechanical defects. Selecting the appropriate parameters ensures that the predictive models are both specific and sensitive to operational changes, a crucial aspect for reliable forecasting in complex engineering systems (Chauhan & Singh, 2019; Chuku et al., 2023).

Table 1: Investigated tugboat characteristics

Characteristics	Values
LOA	16m
Beam	5.4m
Draught	2.6m
Displacement	59 ton
Complement	16
main engines	2 X DooSan
Gearboxes	2 X Dong-I Industry Co
Propellers	2 X FPP
Design speed	11.5 knot

The non-availability of the boat for certain times due to breakdown maintenance could be minimized with the use of PDM instead of preventive maintenance, as is being done today, in which the intervals between stops are fixed and empirically defined. The purpose of this case study is to deal with the development of a model capable of predicting failures in the operation of

the propulsion systems, which would enable the implementation of a PDM technique for locally constructed tugboats. The framework for achieving the PDM model is adapted from Prediction of Main Engine Failure by ANN and Improving Failure Analysis by Combining FTA and FMECA.

Figure 3: Flow Diagram of the Research Framework

Predictive Modelling: Predictive modelling is the central phase of the framework, and a variety of different maintenance strategies and techniques were considered in this phase. In this study, ANN and/or FTA were combined with FMECA. FTA is a top-down method that is used to map the relationships between events, such as subsystem failures and their causes. On the other hand, the FMECA is a reliability evaluation/design technique that examines the potential failure modes within a system and its equipment, in order to determine the effects on equipment and system performance.

Each potential failure mode is classified according to its impact on operational success and personnel/equipment safety. The FMECA is composed of two separate analyses, the Failure

Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA) and the Criticality Analysis (CA). An aspect of this work focus on FMEA. The key idea is to apply FTA and FMEA successively. First, a system-level FTA is performed, which results in a set of failure modes. Using FMEA, the criticality of the failure modes is assessed to select only the critical system-level failure modes. For each of them, a function level FTA is performed, followed by an FMEA on those failure modes. Finally, component-level FTA and FMEA are performed on the critical function level failure modes.

Figure 4 illustrates this framework, showing health transitions governed by probabilities p_{ij} between states i and j . This theoretical model allows maintenance planners to predict future states and allocate resources pre-emptively.

Figure 4: State-Transition Diagram of Equipment Degradation (Markov Chain) (Chiachio et al., 2019)

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

AI techniques, ANN, can be employed to optimize the engine's maintenance and reduction of downtime by analyzing large datasets of engine component failures and performance metrics (Rakopoulos, 2015). An ANN is a powerful tool for modelling complex relationships between input and output variables. In the context of ship propulsion system failure, an ANN can be used to predict various propulsion parameters (e.g., main engine, gearbox) based on operation. This can help optimize performance and inform the design of new plants. A popular statistic for evaluating the success of regression models,

MSE calculates the average of the squared differences between the target variable's actual and projected values.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \tag{1}$$

MSE is the Mean Square Error, n is the number of data points, y_i is the actual value of the target variable for the i-th data point, \hat{y}_i is the predicted value of the target variable for the i-th data point. The forward pass of a basic ANN can be expressed as:

$$y = (Wx + b) \tag{2}$$

Where x denotes input data, W the weight matrices, b the bias terms, and (\cdot) the activation function. This formulation provides the theoretical backbone for extracting hierarchical features from vibration, acoustic, thermal, and other sensor inputs within a marine propulsion

system. The model architecture of the ANN consists of three layers, namely the input, hidden, and output layers.

ANN Architecture

The ANN in this code is a type of AI used for regression tasks, predicting continuous propulsive component variables and other engine parameters. The ANN learns complex relationships between the input data and how its output data affects this input data through training. The ANN is trained using the `fitnet` function in MATLAB, which sets up and trains the neural network using input-output pairs.

$$net = fitn(hidden\ layer\ size) \quad (3)$$

$$[net, tr] = tra(net, input_train', ouput_train') \quad (4)$$

The training process adjusts the weights and biases of the ANN using back-propagation to minimize the prediction error. The `train` function uses a data-set split into training and validation sets to optimize the network. These predictions are then compared with the actual values to evaluate the model's performance. Once trained, the ANN is used to make predictions on both the training and validation sets:

$$Predicted_train = n(input_train') \quad (5)$$

$$predicted_val = n(input_val') \quad (6)$$

Artificial Neural Network Model for Engine Failure Prediction (5-8-1 Architecture)

Figure 5: **Architecture diagram** of the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) for **engine failure prediction** (Raptodimos & Lazakis 2016)

Fault Tree Analysis

As stated previously, FTA is a top-down approach to analyze the reliability of systems by modelling the logical relationships between component failures and the overall system failure. In this analysis, a combination of OR and AND gates is used to model the FTA. Central to

reliability engineering is the reliability function, $R(t)$, which describes the probability that equipment or a system will operate without failure over a defined period. The reliability function is expressed as:

$$R(t) = e^{-(t/\eta)^\beta} \tag{7}$$

Where t denotes time, η is the characteristic life, and β is the shape parameter representing the nature of the failure rate (ReliaWiki, 2019).

The reliability of each component is modelled using the exponential distribution is (Patil, 2013).

$$R(t) = e^{-\lambda st} \tag{8}$$

Figure 6: Fault Tree for Tug Abun propulsion system (Adapted from Knežević et al., 2020)

Figure 7: Fault Tree for Tug Abun Starboard Main Engine (Knežević et al., 2020).

For components connected in an OR gate, the combined reliability is given as

$$R_{oR} = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - R_i) \quad (9)$$

This represents the probability that at least one of the components will fail, causing the OR gate to fail. For components connected in an AND gate, the combined reliability is the product of

individual reliability. This represents the probability that all components must fail for the AND gate to fail (Waghmode, 2004).

$$R_{AND} = \prod_{i=1}^n R_i$$

$$(10)$$

OR Gate 1:

$$R_{OR1} = 1 - (1 - R_{GB})(1 - R_{ME})(1 - R_P)(1 - R_S) \quad (11)$$

OR Gate 2

$$R_{OR2} = 1 - (1 - R_{TC})(1 - R_G)(1 - R_I)(1 - R_{SS})(1 - R_{AC}) \quad (12)$$

AND Gate

$$R_{AND} = (1 - R_{ST})(1 - R_F)(1 - R_{LO})(1 - R_{SW})(1 - R_{FW}) \quad (13)$$

Where

RME is the main engine reliability

RGB is the gearbox reliability

Rp is the Propeller reliability

RS is the Shaft reliability

RTC is the turbocharger reliability

RI is the Injector reliability

RAC is the Air Cooler reliability

RSS is the Subsystem reliability

RFW is the Freshwater System reliability

RSW is the Seawater System reliability

RLO is the Lube Oil System reliability

RF is the Fuel System reliability

RST is the Starting System reliability

Each component reliability $R_{J=1}$ is given as

RG is the Governor's reliability

$$R_1 = (1 - F_1)$$

The risk priority number of the system is expressed mathematically as:

Where F is the failure rate of the component

$$RPN = S \times O \times D \quad (16)$$

The overall system reliability

$$R_{OVERALL} = (1 - F_1)(1 - F_2)(1 - F_3) \dots \dots \dots (15)$$

The reliability of the main engine is given by combining the reliability of the OR and the AND gates. These equations model the logical relationships between component failures and provide a comprehensive view of the system's

reliability. The overall system reliability is the product of the reliability of the components. The key idea is to perform an FTA to identify failure modes and then use an FMEA to assess the

criticality of each failure mode top-down at three different levels.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Developed ANN-FTA-FMECA Model

Artificial Neural Network

Figure 9 illustrates the performance of a predictive model for the fuel system failures, comparing actual occurrences against predicted failures. For the fuel system components, the

actual failures, represented by the blue line, show a value of 10 failure for the fuel transfer pump, 40 failures for the fuel lift pump, 75 for the fuel filters, 30 for the injection pump, 40 for the

strainers, 100 for injectors, 5 for the non-return valve, and 10 for the delivery pipes,

Figure 9: Main Engine (Fuel System): Actual vs Predicted Failures

The model demonstrates a strong alignment with the actual data, especially for components like the injectors, which had the highest number of failures of 100, with the model predicting a very close value of 95. The operation of the propulsion power plants could be greatly enhanced by the application of an ANN to forecast the failures. Maintenance could be changed from a reactive to a proactive strategy in order to precisely forecast when and where problems are likely to occur. For instance, engineers can plan maintenance or unit replacement before failure happens by knowing that injectors will fail 95 times over the period under review. This helps to avoid unplanned and expensive downtime. By optimizing maintenance schedules, the ANN can minimize

operational delays and the need for emergency repairs. Other subsystems also demonstrated same predictive capacity.

For several different engine components, Figure 10 compares the actual and expected number of failures. The orange broken line shows the expected number of failures, while the blue line shows the actual number. The predictive model's accuracy is demonstrated by the two lines' extreme proximity to one another throughout the graph. Ten actual and nine predicted failures occurred in the crank case, five actual and five forecasted failures occurred in the crankshaft, and ten actual and eleven expected failures occurred in the camshaft. The governor experienced 15 failures in reality, compared to the 16 that were anticipated.

Figure 10: Main Engine Block Assembly: Actual vs Predicted Failures

The liners had 40 actual failures and 38 predicted. For the connecting rods, both the actual and predicted failures were 10. The big/small ends bearing had 20 actual failures and 22 predicted. The thrust washer had 10 actual and 10 predicted failures. The pistons had 15 actual and 14 predicted failures. The component with the highest number of failures was the piston rings, which had 75 actual failures and a very close predicted value of 72. Finally, the cylinder heads had 20 actual failures and 21 from prediction. The consistent proximity of the predicted values to the actual values across all components indicates that the model is a reliable tool for forecasting propulsion systems component failures. It also had a low MSE of 3.55 and MAE of 1.73.

4.2 Training, Validation and Test Data.

Numerous examples from the training phase indicate that the model was exposed to a range of

propulsion system operating situations, which enabled it to pick up intricate correlations between different operational parameters. In order for the ANN to manage nonlinear performance indicators, such the correlation between engine speed and emission and fuel injection time, this degree of training was essential. The predictive model's accuracy is indicated by how closely the bars in the validation and test stages resemble the zero-error line. Based on data inputs, the ANN may thereby improve engine performance in real-time, optimizing fuel usage, lowering pollutants, and increasing power output.

The linear graph represents the ANN model's training performances shown in Figure 11, with the target values ranging from 0 to 1200, plotted against the corresponding model outputs, which follows a linear relationship of $output = 0.91 * target + 1.0$. The graph aligns closely with the ideal linear

Graphs.

Figure 11 Graph of ANN Training, Validation and Test

By identifying the underlying patterns in the training data, this linear connection illustrates how well the ANN learned. The model's capacity to make use of the training data is demonstrated by the steady and proportionate alignment between the predicted and output values. A linear graph like this indicates that the ANN has successfully learned the input-output mapping for this particular task. The accuracy of the model is demonstrated by the observed proximity between the actual and predicted values over the whole range. The correctness is visually confirmed by this graph. Resilience and efficiency of the ANN in this study's linear relationship approximation.

The linear graph of the validation results for the ANN with a target-output relationship of $\text{output} = 0.92 * \text{target} + 9.8$ demonstrates a strong linear fit. The linear relationship indicates that the MultiLayer Perceptron (MLP) has successfully learned and replicated the underlying pattern.

Given that the validation results closely resemble the ideal linear trend, the graph validates the model's capacity to generalize results. The model's accuracy in predicting the target values over the whole range is indicated by the close clustering of dots around the regression line. This linear graph indicates that the linear correlation between the input objectives and

their corresponding outputs has been successfully captured by the ANN. It demonstrates its capacity to model and forecast data interactions.

Multi-Layer Perceptron Function Fit and Best Validation

The linear graph, as shown in Figure 12 illustrates the training progression of an MLP for thermodynamic optimization of the propulsion plant, showcasing its best validation performance at epoch 3 with an MSE of 3.746×10^{-6} . The y-axis, representing MSE, spans from 10^{-15} to 10^{-5} , providing a clear visualization of the model's fine-tuning. Across the 4000 epochs, ranging from 0 to 6000 on the x-axis, a consistent downward trend in MSE is observed, indicating improved convergence and learning.

The sharp decrease in MSE within the first few epochs highlights the rapid initial learning of the model. This progression suggests efficient model adaptation to the training data, reaching an optimal point at epoch 3000. The graph's linearity signifies stable training without overfitting or underfitting, ensuring robust generalization to new data. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of the MLP in achieving thermodynamic optimization for the marine propulsion plant, with the visual representation providing a concise overview of the performance throughout the training process.

Figure 12: Graph of ANN Best Validation Performance

Reliability

The subsystem failure probability graph shown in Figure 13 illustrates the relative vulnerability of each component group contributing to the overall propulsion system unreliability. The highest probability was observed in the fuel

system ($P = 0.1817$), indicating it as the most failure-prone subsystem due to frequent occurrences such as injector and filter blockages. This was followed by the engine block assembly ($P = 0.1299$) and main engine cooling system ($P = 0.0672$), both critical for maintaining propulsion stability and thermal regulation.

Figure 13: Subsystem Failures

Moderate failure probabilities were recorded in gearbox cooling ($P = 0.0580$) and main engine lubricating oil system ($P = 0.0390$), signifying poor cooling and inadequate lubrication (viscosity loss). Subsystems such as shafting ($P =$

0.0065), coupling, bearing, and propeller ($P = 0.0000$) show near-negligible probabilities, implying effective structural reliability. Overall, the combined subsystem probabilities yielded a

top event probability ($P_{top} = 0.5882$), suggesting above-average overall system reliability.

Conclusion

A multi-layer perceptron network model for early failure detection in marine propulsion systems was created in this study. This was combined with options depending on dependability and risk, such as FMECA and FTA. The dependability framework analysis was used to guide the model's 4000+ epochs of MATLAB operation. The model's outcome indicates that the goal was accomplished.

The relative susceptibility of each component group that contributes to the overall unreliability of the propulsion system is displayed in the subsystem failure probability graph. The fuel system had the highest likelihood ($P = 0.1817$), suggesting that it is the subsystem most likely to fail because of frequent events like injector and filter clogs. The main engine cooling system ($P = 0.0672$) and engine block assembly ($P = 0.1299$) came next, both of which are essential for preserving thermal control and propulsion stability. The primary engine lubricating oil system ($P = 0.0390$) and gearbox cooling ($P = 0.0580$) showed moderate failure probability, indicating insufficient lubrication (viscosity loss)

REFERENCES

Adumene, S. & Nitonye, S. (2018). Application of Probabilistic Model for Marine Steam System Failure Analysis under Uncertainty, *Open Journal of Safety Science and Technology*, 8(2), 21-34.

and poor cooling. The near-negligible probability of subsystems including shafting ($P = 0.0065$), coupling, bearing, and propeller ($P = 0.0000$) suggest effective structural reliability. A top event probability ($P_{top} = 0.5882$) was obtained from the sum of the subsystem probabilities, indicating above-average overall system reliability.

The results from the field data achieved 95 per cent accuracy for the fuel injection system and about 94.6 per cent accuracy on the other subsystems. The percentage accuracy is in line with the objective of this research. The results from the prediction using the Artificial Neural Network were subjected to reliability analysis. This was done to assess the robustness of the predictive model. Pertinently, an overall system reliability of 58.82 per cent was achieved. The efficiency of the combined ANN-FTA-FMECA framework is demonstrated by the attainment of 95 percent and 94.6% accuracy on the prediction of failure for the four injection systems and other subsystems of the marine propulsion system, respectively. If properly applied, this approach would decrease maintenance expenses, improve service life, and decrease downtime for the vessel's propulsion systems.

<https://doi.org/10.4236/ojsst.2018.82003>
<http://www.scirp.org/journal/ojsst>

Afini, A., Robinson, U. A. & Nitonye, S. (2025). Engine Performance Prediction Under Different Loading Conditions: A Comparative Approach, "Irish

- International Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences” 9 (1) 19-28, Retrieved from <https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/ijjeas/article/view/953/1018>
- Ahmed, S., Li, T., Huang, S., & Cao, J. (2023). Dynamic and quantitative risk assessment of cruise ship pod propulsion system failure: An integrated Type-2 Fuzzy-Bayesian approach. *Ocean Engineering*, 279, Article 114601.
- Ajinwo, K. O.; Tamunodukobipi, D. & Nitonye, S. (2025) Performance Prediction of a Marine Diesel Engine under Varied Operating Conditions Using Artificial Intelligence, “Irish International Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences” 9 (1) 1-18, Retrieved from <https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/ijjeas/article/view/945/1009>
- Budimir, D., Medić, D., Ružić, V., & Kulej, M. (2025). Integrated approach to marine engine maintenance optimization: Weibull analysis, Markov chains, and DEA model. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 13(4), 798.
- Celeux, G., Corset, F., Lannoy, A., & Ricard, B. (2009). Designing a Bayesian network for preventive maintenance from expert opinions in a rapid and reliable way [Preprint]. arXiv. Retrieved June 23, 2025, from <https://arxiv.org/abs/0905.2864>
- Chauhan, R., & Singh, M. (2019). Predictive maintenance using machine learning: A case study on ship engine data. *International Journal of Prognostics and Health Management*, 10(1), 1–11. <https://www.phmsociety.org/node/2533>
- Chiachio, J., Jalón Ramírez, M. L., Chiachio, M., & Kolios, A. (2019). A Markov chains prognostics framework for complex degradation processes. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, 195, 106621.
- Chuku, J. A., Adumene, S., Orji, C.U., Theophilus-Johnson, K., & Nitonye, S. (2023), Dynamic Failure Analysis of Ship Energy Systems Using an Adaptive Machine Learning Formalism. *Journal of Computational and Cognitive Engineering*, <https://ojs.bonviewpress.com/index.php/JCCE/article/view/491> DOI: 10.47852
- Daya, A. A., & Lazakis, I. (2022). Investigating ship system performance degradation and failure criticality using FMECA and artificial neural networks. In *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on*

- Maritime Technology and Engineering (MARTECH) (pp. 1–11). Lisbon, Portugal. application-199552/ Retrieved June 19, 2025
- Daya, A. A., & Lazakis, I. (2023). Developing an advanced reliability analysis framework for marine systems operations and maintenance. *Ocean Engineering*, 272, 113766.
- Daya, A. A., & Lazakis, I. (2024). Systems reliability and data driven analysis for marine machinery maintenance planning and decision making. *Machines*, 12(5), 294.
- de Assis, E. M., Figueirôa, C. L. S., Lima, G. C., Salles, G. M. de O., & Pinto, A. (2021). Comparison between maintenance policies based on q-Weibull and Weibull models. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, ahead-of-print (ahead-of-print). Retrieved June 23, 2025, from <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJQRM-09-2019-0283>
- DNV, & Propulsion Analytics. (2021). Propulsion Analytics and DNV join forces on condition-based maintenance ship application. Retrieved June 19, 2025, from <https://www.dnv.com/news/propulsion-analytics-and-dnv-join-forces-on-condition-basedmaintenance-ship->
- Elmdoost-Gashti, M., Shafiee, M., & Bozorgi-Amiri, A. (2023). Enhancing resilience in marine propulsion systems by adopting machine learning technology for predicting failures and prioritizing maintenance activities. *Journal of Marine Engineering & Technology*, 23(1), 18–32.
- Emovon, I., (2016). Failure Mode and Effects Analysis of Ship Systems Using an Integrated Dempster Shafer Theory and Electre Method. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology* 10(1) 45 - 50.
- Eriksen, S., Utne, I. B., & Lützen, M. (2021). An RCM approach for assessing reliability challenges and maintenance needs of unmanned cargo ships. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, 210, 107550.
- Fazle, A. B., Proadhan, R. K., & Islam, M. (2023). AI-powered predictive failure analysis in pressure vessels using real-time sensor fusion: Enhancing industrial safety and infrastructure reliability. *American Journal of Scholarly Research and Innovation*, 2(2), 102–134.
- Fontalvo Herrera, T. J., Banquez Maturana, A. G., & Mendoza Villero, K. (2024).

- Performance of a concurrent parallel production system through new operating curves of Six Sigma metrics. *Production*, 34, e20240010.
- Garbatov, Y., & Georgiev, P. (2024). Markovian Maintenance Planning of Ship Propulsion System Accounting for CII and System Degradation. *Energies*, 17(16), 4123.
- Guo, Y., & Zhang, J. (2023). Fault diagnosis of marine diesel engines under partial set and cross working conditions based on transfer learning. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 11(8), 1527.
- Gupta, G., Ghasemian, H., & Janvekar, A. A. (2021). A novel failure mode effect and criticality analysis (FMECA) using fuzzy rule-based method: A case study of industrial centrifugal pump. *Engineering Failure Analysis*, 123, 105305.
- Kim, D., Lee, S., & Lee, J. (2019). An ensemble-based approach to anomaly detection in marine engine sensor streams for efficient condition monitoring and analysis. *Sensors*, 20(24), 7285.
- Kiran, D. R. (2017). Reliability engineering. In *Total Quality Management: Key Concepts and Case Studies* (pp. 391-402). Butterworth-Heinemann.
- Knežević, V., Orović, J., Stazić, L., & Čulin, J. (2020). Fault tree analysis and failure diagnosis of marine diesel engine turbocharger system. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 8(12), 1004.
- Lazakis, I., Raptodimos, Y., & Varelas, T. (2018). Predicting ship machinery system condition through analytical reliability tools and artificial neural networks. *Ocean Engineering*, 152, 404-415.
- Molęda, M., Ding, W., Sunderam, V., & Mrozek, D. (2022). From corrective to predictive maintenance—a review of maintenance approaches for the power industry. *Sensors*, 23(13), 5970.
- Morato, P. G., Papakonstantinou, K. G., Andriotis, C. P., Nielsen, J. S., & Rigo, P. (2020). Optimal inspection and maintenance planning for deteriorating structural components through dynamic Bayesian networks and Markov decision processes. *Structural Safety*, 94, 102140.
- Neesae A. L., Theophilus-Johnson K. & Nitonye S. (2026) Developing Artificial Neural Network (ANN) Based Predictive Maintenance Techniques For Marine Propulsion Systems. *Irish International Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, 10(1), 50-72.

- <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18773110>
- Nolan, D. P. (2017). Fault-tree analysis. In Fire pump arrangements at industrial facilities. Elsevier. Retrieved June 23, 2025, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/engineering/fault-treeanalysis>
- Pagán Rubio, J. A., Hernández Grau, J., & Albaladejo Hernández, D. (2019). Improvements of a failure database for marine diesel engines using the RCM and simulations. *Energies*, 13(1), 104.
- Patil, R. (2013). An Overview of Fault Tree Analysis (FTA) Method for Reliability Analysis. *Journal of Engineering Research and Studies*. 4. 6-8.
- Peng, B. (2024). A review of research on marine main propulsion systems. *Journal of Education and Educational Research*, 9(1), 189-192.
- Rakopoulos, C.D. (2015). Comparative Evaluation of Predictive Models for the Performance and Emissions of a Diesel Engine Fueled with Biodiesel. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 101, 431-443.
- Raptodimos, Y. & Lazakis, I. (2016). An Artificial Neural Network Approach for Predicting the Performance of Ship Machinery Equipment. *Maritime Safety and Operations 2016 Conference Proceedings*.
- ReliaWiki. (2019). The Weibull distribution. ReliaWiki. Retrieved June 23, 2025, from https://www.reliawiki.com/index.php/The_Weibull_Distribution
- Ruijters, E., & Stoelinga, M. (2015). Fault tree analysis: A survey of the state-of-the-art in modeling, analysis and tools. *Computer Science Review*, 15-16, 29-62.
- Sezer, Ş. İ., Ceylan, B. O., Akyüz, E., & Arslan, Ö. (2022). D-S evidence based FMECA approach to assess potential risks in ballast water system (BWS) on-board tanker ship. *Journal of Ocean Engineering and Science*, 1-12.
- Simion, D., Postolache, F., Fleacă, B., & Fleacă, E. (2023). AI-driven predictive maintenance in modern maritime transport—Enhancing operational efficiency and reliability. *Applied Sciences*, 14(20), 9439.
- Sun, J., Ren, H., Duan, Y., Yang, X., Wang, D., & Tang, H. (2024). Fusion of multi-layer attention mechanisms and CNN-LSTM for fault prediction in marine diesel engines. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 12(6), 990.

- Tamunodukobipi, D. & Nitonye, S. (2019). Numerical Analysis of the RAP Characteristics of a Catamaran Vessel for Niger Delta Pliability, *Journal of Power and Energy Engineering*, 7(10), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jpee.2019.710001> <http://www.scirp.org/journal/jpee>
- Tripathi, A., & Prasad, M. H. (2024). RCM-based optimization of maintenance strategies for marine diesel engines using genetic algorithms. *International Journal of System Assurance Engineering and Management*, 15, 3757-3775.
- Waghmode L. Y. (2024) some studies on Total life cycle costs of an industrial product or a system, Dissertation of ME Design, Shivaji University, Kolhapur 2004.
- Wang, S., Zhao, Y., & Chen, N. (2022). Fault diagnosis of ship power station based on LSTM neural network algorithm. *Vibroengineering PROCEDIA*, 41, 204-210.
- Wärtsilä. (2019). the new age propulsion condition monitoring service: Key to predictive maintenance and optimal uptime. <https://www.wartsila.com/insights/article/the-new-agepropulsion-condition-monitoring-service-key-to-predictive-maintenance-and-optimaluptime>
- Youssef, A., Noura, H., Amrani, A. E., Adel, E. M., & Ouladsine, M. (2024). A survey on data-driven fault diagnostic techniques for marine diesel engines [Preprint].
- arXiv. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2404.10363> Retrieved June 19, 2025
- Zheng, H., Paiva, A. R., & Gurciullo, C. S. (2020). Advancing from predictive maintenance to intelligent maintenance with AI and IIoT [Preprint]. arXiv. Retrieved June 23, 2025, from <https://arxiv.org/abs/2009.00351>